

Diversity and Cultural Significance of Wild Edible Macrofungi: A Case Study in Dhemaji District of Assam, India

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Abstract

Wild edible macrofungi form an important part of the food culture and livelihood systems of rural communities in Assam. This study, conducted in Dhemaji district, documents the diversity of wild edible mushrooms and explores their socio-cultural significance among indigenous groups. Field surveys and ethnomycological interviews during 2025–2026 revealed nine edible species, including *Calvatia craniiformis*, *Coprinellus micaceus*, *Psilocybe cubensis*, *Leucocoprinus cepaestipes*, *Macrolepiota* sp., *Termitomyces heimii*, *Termitomyces clypeatus*, *Termitomyces schimperi*, and *Psathyrella tuberculata*. Local communities rely on traditional knowledge to identify safe species, using ecological cues and morphological traits. Mushrooms are consumed as seasonal delicacies, incorporated into traditional dishes, and hold roles in rituals, folk medicine, and local markets. The findings highlight both the biological diversity and the socio-cultural importance of wild edible macrofungi in Dhemaji, emphasizing the need for systematic documentation and sustainable management.

Keywords: *Wild edible macrofungi, Dhemaji district, Assam, ethnomycology, cultural practices, biodiversity*

Introduction

The Dhemaji district of Assam, situated in the floodplains of the Brahmaputra River and adjoining the Eastern Himalayan region of Arunachal Pradesh, is recognized as part of a rich biodiversity zone. Its ecological setting, characterized by forests, wetlands, and agricultural landscapes, supports diverse flora and fauna, including a wide variety of wild mushrooms. The people of Dhemaji maintain close interaction with nature and depend on it for food, medicine, and cultural practices. Traditional knowledge systems enable local communities to recognize and utilize useful wild plants and fungi, reflecting a deep-rooted ethnobiological relationship with their environment [1].

Wild edible macrofungi are widely collected during the monsoon season. Local communities possess indigenous knowledge to distinguish edible species from poisonous ones, and mushroom collection has become an important seasonal activity. These mushrooms are consumed as part of the daily diet and also hold cultural significance among ethnic groups such as the Mising, Bodo, and Assamese rural populations [2]. Beyond their nutritional value, mushrooms are embedded in socio-cultural practices, including rituals, folk medicine, and local market economies [3].

Despite their importance, systematic documentation of mushroom diversity and cultural practices in Dhemaji remains limited. This research aims to document the diversity of wild edible mushrooms in Dhemaji and analyze their socio-cultural significance, thereby contributing to the broader understanding of ethnomycology and sustainable resource use in Northeast India.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in five blocks i.e. Dhemaji, Sissibargaon, Murkongseleck, Muchkhuwa and Bordoloni of Dhemaji district (Latitude: 27°28'48" N; Longitude: 94°34'48" E) during 2024–2025(Fig-1), covering diverse habitats such as forest edges, agricultural fields, bamboo groves, and homestead gardens. Field surveys were conducted in the monsoon months (June–September), when mushroom fruiting is most abundant. Ethnomycological data were collected through semi-structured interviews with 50 local foragers and elders, focusing on traditional knowledge of edible species, identification practices, and cultural uses.

Collected specimens were identified using standard mycological keys [4]. Morphological features such as cap, gills, and spore prints were recorded. Participant observation was undertaken in households and local markets to document mushroom-related practices, while rituals, taboos, and folk narratives were recorded through oral accounts and direct observation.

Fig.-1: Study areas in Dhemaji, Assam, India

Results and Discussion

A total of nine wild edible mushroom species were documented from different habitats of Dhemaji district. Representative species included *Calvatia craniiformis*, *Coprinellus micaceus*, *Psilocybe cubensis*, *Leucocoprinus cepaestipes*, *Macrolepiota* sp., *Termitomyces heimii*, *Termitomyces clypeatus*, *Termitomyces schimperi*, and *Psathyrella tuberculata*, all belonging to the class Basidiomycetes (Table-1 & Fig.- 2).

Seasonal observations indicated peak fruiting during the monsoon months, with *Termitomyces* species showing strong ecological association with termite mounds [1]. Mushrooms were consumed as seasonal delicacies, often prepared with bamboo shoots, fish, or local herbs. Certain species were offered in community feasts, while taboos discouraged harvesting of poisonous lookalikes. Knowledge of mushroom identification was transmitted orally across generations, with women and elders playing a central role. Economically, mushrooms were sold in weekly markets, providing supplementary income during the monsoon season [3]. Five edible species of macrofungi were reported from Kokrajhar District of BTAD area, Assam [5].

Ethnomycological insights revealed reliance on morphological traits such as cap shape, gill color, and ecological associations (e.g., termite mounds, bamboo groves). Folk narratives linked mushrooms to fertility, abundance, and forest spirits, while some species were used in traditional remedies for digestive health and fever.

Traditional Techniques for Identification of Wild Edible Mushrooms

Indigenous knowledge has long been used to identify wild edible mushrooms by different community of assam viz., Bodo, Karbi, mishing, Garo etc., based on observable morphological and sensory characteristics. Some Traditional techniques recorded during the study were listed below-

Table-1: Traditional Techniques for Identification of Wild Edible Mushrooms

Sl. No.	Observation	Character
1.	Development of a distinct ring on the stipe at maturity	The formation of a distinct ring (annulus) on the stipe at middle age is considered an important for recognizing feature in certain edible mushroom species.
2.	Pleasant odour aiding recognition.	Edible mushrooms are often characterized by a mild and pleasant odour, which supports in their recognition in the field.
3.	Fruiting body and gills turning red-brown when harvested.	In some species, the fruiting body and gills display a reddish-brown coloration upon harvesting, serving as a distinguishing trait.

4.	Stipe changing to brown upon breakage.	The stipe might turn brown or undergo other color changes when fragmented, which can be used as an identification criterion.
5.	Release of Color in Water	When the stipe is deep in water, certain mushrooms release a brown pigment, which is conventionally used as an additional identification test

Table-1: List of wild edibles macrofungal

Sl no.	Names of the collected Macrofungi	Class of the fungi	Habitat of growing
1	<i>Calvatia craniiformis</i> (Schwein.) Fr. ex De Toni (1888)	Basidiomycetes	Grasslands and open soils
2	<i>Coprinellus micaceus</i> (Bull.) Vilgalys, Hopple & Jacq. Johnson (2001)	Basidiomycetes	Decaying wood and stumps
3	<i>Leucocoprinus cepaestipes</i> (Sowerby) Singer (1948)	Basidiomycetes	Nutrient-rich soils, dung, and grassy areas
4	<i>Macrolepiota sp.</i>	Basidiomycetes	Forest edges and grasslands
5	<i>Psilocybe cubensis</i> (Earle) Singer (1948)	Basidiomycetes	Dead or decaying hardwood logs and stumps.
6	<i>Psathyrella tuberculata</i> (Pat.) A.H.Sm., 1972	Basidiomycetes	Moist soils, decaying organic matter
7	<i>Termitomyces heimii</i> Nataranjan(1979)	Basidiomycetes	Nutrient-rich soils, often in grasslands, gardens, or wood chips
8	<i>Termitomyces clypeatus</i> R.Heim(1959)	Basidiomycetes	Termite mounds
9	<i>Termitomyces schimperi</i> (pat.) R. Heim (1942)	Basidiomycetes	Termite mounds

Fig.- 2: Wild edible macrofungi- a. *Calvatia craniiformis*, b. *Macrolepiota* sp., c. *Psilocybe cubensis*, d. *Termitomyces schimperi*, e. *Termitomyces clypeatus*, f. *Termitomyces heimii*

Conclusion

Wild edible macrofungi in Dhemaji district represent a vital intersection of biodiversity and cultural heritage. Their diversity enriches local diets and provides seasonal nutritional support, while traditional practices ensure safe identification and transmission of ethnomycological knowledge across generations. Beyond food, mushrooms hold cultural value through rituals, folk medicine, and

local market economies. Promoting sustainable harvesting and documenting indigenous knowledge can strengthen food security and preserve cultural identity. Future research should emphasize nutritional profiling, domestication potential, and policy integration to enhance the role of wild edible macrofungi in regional development and sustainable resource management.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest: The authors declares that there are no financial, personal, professional, or Institutional relationships that could be perceived as a conflict of interest or as having influenced the research or its interpretation in this manuscript.

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